

On the adsorption of *n*-butane on alkyl imidazolium ionic liquids with different anions using a new molecular beam setup

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ABSTRACT

The adsorption of reactants is an elementary step in the interaction of molecules with liquid or solid surfaces. We recently reported on the trapping of *n*-butane on the frozen surfaces of ionic liquids (ILs), namely, 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide ILs ($[C_nC_1Im][Tf_2N]$; $n = 1, 2, 3,$ and 8). To study the influence of the anion, we now present results concerning the trapping of *n*-butane on 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate ILs ($[C_nC_1Im][PF_6]$; $n = 2, 4,$ and 8), that is, ILs with a smaller anion. The adsorption energies close to zero coverage are determined from the temperature dependence of the initial trapping probability using a novel approach. For both groups of ILs, the binding energy is dominated by the interaction of *n*-butane with the alkyl chain of the cation, whereas the ionic headgroups contribute only weakly. Comparing ILs with different alkyl chains at the IL cation, we find that the adsorption strength of *n*-butane increases with increasing length of the alkyl chain. In addition, detailed information on the new setup and the data analysis is provided.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The dynamic adsorption process of a gas molecule on a surface followed by possible physical and chemical transformations is of fundamental interest. Corresponding investigations of the relevant gas/surface interactions have typically been performed using supersonic molecular beams in ultra-high vacuum (UHV) for various molecules and solid surfaces in the past.^{1–8} Detailed information on the adsorption/desorption process, preferred orientation and bonding of the molecules to the surface, surface diffusion, bond activation, and chemical reactions has been obtained.^{1–19} Understanding these processes at the fundamental level is imperative for several applications such as heterogeneous catalysis, thin film growth, or separation technology.^{11,20–22}

The investigation of dynamic processes at the surfaces and interfaces of liquids is equally important as for solids. However, sophisticated instrumentation is necessary to apply UHV-based

molecular beam methods to explore the dynamics at the surfaces of conventional aqueous or organic liquids that are volatile under these conditions.^{23,24} In these studies, the evaporating liquids are often supplied as a microjet or spread on a rotating wheel, which ensures their continuous replacement.^{25–27} As an alternative to conventional liquids, a special class of liquid materials, that is, ionic liquids (ILs), can be chosen as model systems for this purpose: Due to their extremely rich structural diversity combined with a negligible vapor pressure,^{28,29} ILs are ideal candidates for studying liquid surfaces under UHV conditions using the powerful surface science analytical toolbox (see, e.g., Refs. 30–36 and references therein).

ILs are per definition liquid below 100 °C, some of them even at room temperature. They comprise only anions and cations, such as conventional salts.^{37–39} Due to their tunable physicochemical properties, they have been adapted to specific applications, ranging from solvents,^{40,41} lubricants,⁴² electrolytes,^{43,44} acid scavengers,⁴⁵ and green chemistry⁴⁶ to catalysis.^{47–49} Since 2005/2006, ILs are in

the focus of surface science studies, and this new field of “ionic liquid surface science”⁵⁰ has developed a detailed understanding of the steady state or static properties of the vacuum/IL interface, such as surface composition, surface enrichment, and orientation effects.^{30,31,33–36,51,52} For specific systems, even chemical reactions in ionic liquids have been studied (see Ref. 53 and references therein). The preparation of ultrathin IL films by physical vapor deposition made it possible to also study the fundamental properties of the IL/support interface,^{54–56} which play a pivotal role in IL-based catalysis.

Based on ILs, two new concepts have been introduced in the area of catalysis, that is, supported ionic liquid phase (SILP)^{57–60} and solid catalyst with ionic liquid layer (SCILL).^{61,62} In these concepts, a thin IL layer coats the catalyst support, which enhances the selectivity, product distribution, and yields. In both, one crucial step is the transfer of gas molecules through the gas/IL interface. Despite this importance, only a few reports on the gas/IL interface dynamics exist. These concern adsorption/desorption and quantum-state-resolved scattering processes of small molecules.^{63–68} Due to the small number of studies, the understanding of gas adsorption on IL surfaces and the subsequent interaction, diffusion, and transport is rather limited. This motivated us to build a novel UHV chamber combining a supersonic molecular beam, a rotatable mass spectrometer, and facilities for *in situ* X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) to investigate the interaction of gases with non-volatile liquids. The liquid sample is positioned horizontally to avoid dripping off the support. To enable normal beam incidence, the molecular beam is mounted vertically, in contrast to most existing setups with a horizontal molecular beam. Recently, we published the first results

on the dynamic interaction of *n*-butane with imidazolium-based bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide ILs with a varying alkyl chain length at the cation.⁶⁹

Herein, we focus on the interaction of *n*-butane with related ILs, that is, 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate, $[C_nC_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ ($n = 2, 4, \text{ and } 8$). We compare the data to those from our previous study on $[C_nC_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ to further elucidate the role of the anion in the interaction process. In addition, we will introduce a novel approach to determine the desorption energy of *n*-butane from its temperature-dependent trapping probability in the zero-coverage limit. Moreover, we provide details on the instrumental setup and its characterization.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

The experiments were performed in a newly developed molecular beam setup, which was designed and assembled in-house. An overview of the instrument is presented in Fig. 1. The instrument's name ILID (ionic liquid interface dynamics) refers to its dedication to ionic liquid surface science. The compact instrument consists of (i) the preparation chamber for sample introduction, cleaning and *in situ* sample preparation, (ii) the analysis chamber where most of the measurements are done, and (iii) the three-stage molecular beam setup generating the supersonic molecular beam. All chambers (custom-built by VAb, Vakuum-Anlagenbau GmbH) are pumped by turbomolecular pumps (TP); notably, the first differential pumping stage of the molecular beam is pumped by two TPs. Each TP is backed by a rotary pump. The analysis and preparation

FIG. 1. An overview of the new molecular beam setup with a vertically mounted supersonic beam. (a) Three main parts of the ILID chamber: the preparation chamber (red), analysis chamber (green), and molecular beam setup (yellow). Ports for the analyzer and QMS are labeled in the analysis chamber. (b) A photograph of the complete setup. (c) A picture of the interior of the first pumping stage of the beam chamber. A Mo tube is mounted between two Cu brackets used for heating/cooling, the nozzle is located next to the central thermocouple, and below the nozzle sits the skimmer. (d) A picture of the interior of the analysis chamber. In the background, the (closed) gate valve to the preparation chamber is visible. The picture was taken through the open rotatable flange after dismantling the QMS, which is therefore not visible in this picture. The sample position and the impinging molecular beam are indicated.

chambers are additionally equipped with a combined ion getter and titanium sublimation pump each (see also Fig. S1 and Table S1 of the [supplementary material](#)).

A. Preparation chamber and manipulator

The preparation chamber is equipped with a sputter gun (SPECS IQE 11/35), together with a leak valve for Ar dosing and a four-grid LEED (low energy electron diffraction) setup (SPECS ErLEED 150) to determine the long-range order of single-crystal surfaces or possible adsorbate superstructures. For pressure measurement, a hot-filament ionization gauge is attached to the chamber.

The manipulator (VAb PM 25-800) enables motorized movement along the z -axis by 800 mm and manual movement along the x - and y -axes by ± 25 mm (see also Fig. S2 of the [supplementary material](#)). Manual rotation around the z -axis is possible using a differentially pumped rotary feedthrough, which is pumped by a small ion getter pump. The sample is cooled using liquid N_2 . The temperatures of the manipulator head and of the sample are measured by type K (chromel/alumel) thermocouples. Using a filament below the sample plate, the sample can be heated up to ≈ 450 K by indirect radiation heating. Alternatively, the sample can be heated up to ≈ 1200 K by electron bombardment from the back side with the filament biased with ≈ -1 kV so that emitted electrons are accelerated toward the grounded sample.

The IL samples are introduced into the UHV chamber using a load-lock system. For that purpose, a transferable sample holder system with very reliable temperature readings was adopted for the instrument [see Fig. S2 (bottom) of the [supplementary material](#)]. The IL support, a polycrystalline Ni block ($12 \times 12 \times 4$ mm³; Goodfellow), is fixed with a U-shaped Mo clamp onto a Ta ground plate ($18 \times 15 \times 1$ mm³), which can be grabbed by the wobble stick. The type K thermocouple is inserted into the small hole (0.4 mm diameter and 3 mm depth) of the support, and the two wires are connected to thermocouple contacts, which are electrically insulated from the rest of the sample holder by ceramic spacers. The thermocouple contacts touch the corresponding type K thermocouple contacts of the sample stage in the manipulator head. With this setup, a very accurate and reliable relative measurement of the sample temperature (± 1 K) is achieved (note that absolute temperature accuracy is estimated to be around ± 3 K). Using liquid N_2 , the sample can be cooled down to 88 K.

B. Analysis chamber

The analysis chamber is equipped with a hemispherical electron analyzer (SPECS PHOIBOS 100 1D-DLD) and a dual-anode X-ray gun (SPECS XR 50) for XPS. For molecular beam experiments, a quadrupole mass spectrometer (QMS) with a cross beam ionization source and a secondary electron multiplier as detector (Hiden Analytical 3F RC 301 PIC) is mounted on a rotatable flange, which allows for rotation by $\approx 270^\circ$ around the sample (distance sample–QMS ionization source: 96 mm). Another feature of the analysis chamber is the beam monitor, which is mounted on a small xyz-manipulator. This device consists of a small volume separated from the analysis chamber by an orifice with a diameter of 1.0 mm.⁷⁰ Inside the beam monitor sits a hot-filament ionization gauge, which allows for the

measurement of the stagnation pressure building up if the molecular beam covers the orifice completely. In this way, we can determine the flux of the incoming molecular beam. The chamber is also equipped with a sample flag, which can be used to deflect the molecular beam before it hits the sample surface. This type of sample flag is required for trapping (sticking) probability measurements by the King and Wells method.⁷¹

C. Molecular beam

The molecular beam setup comprises three differentially pumped chambers, referred to as stages 1, 2, and 3. The nozzle in stage 1 [Fig. 1(c)] is a round hole with a 100 μ m diameter in a Mo stagnation tube with an inner diameter of 0.7 mm. The tube is mounted between two mechanical Cu brackets and can be moved by an xyz-manipulator to adjust the position of the nozzle. The nozzle can be resistively heated with the two Cu brackets as electrical contacts. The Cu brackets can be cooled with water so that the surroundings do not overheat if high nozzle temperatures (up to 1300 K) are used. The temperature of the stagnation tube can be measured by two type K thermocouples, one located close to the nozzle and the other one located close to the cooling/heating system. One side of the tube is a dead-end and the other one is connected to the gas inlet system, which can be fed through three mass flow controllers (Bronkhorst EL-FLOW Prestige). Thus, mixtures of up to three gases in any composition can be used in the molecular beam. The gas inlet system comprises a by-pass, which leads directly into stage 1. The by-pass can be used to pump down and purge the gas inlet system (through the nozzle only a limited amount of gas can flow).

The skimmer (Ni; opening diameter: 0.5 mm; Beam Dynamics, Inc.) sits directly below the nozzle and separates stages 1 and 2. It has a sharp edge and a conical form so that the flow of the supersonic jet is obstructed only minimally. Since a sufficiently low pressure in stage 1 is needed, to ensure that the gas reaches the supersonic velocity, stage 1 is pumped by two TPs.

The beam flag, a simple rotatable shutter in stage 2, can be used for rapidly switching the beam on and off. If the beam is blocked, the gas molecules are scattered and almost completely pumped away in stage 2, and only a small pressure rise is observed in stage 3 and the analysis chamber. Stages 2 and 3 are separated by four changeable apertures with diameters of 1.1 mm, 1.9 mm, 2.6 mm, and 3.7 mm. They are used to adjust the beam diameter and the position of the beam spot on the sample (see Fig. S3 of the [supplementary material](#)). A gate valve separates stage 3 and the analysis chamber. If this valve is closed, stages 1, 2, and 3 are completely sealed from the rest of the instrument. Thus, sample preparation and setting up of the molecular beam can be done at the same time.

The n -butane beam used in the present study is produced with the nozzle at room temperature and a gas flow of 1.0 SCCM using the smallest aperture (1.1 mm). The kinetic energy of the unseeded molecular beam was estimated to be 13 kJ/mol, in comparison to Ref. 59, and the resulting n -butane flux was $2.0 \cdot 10^{13}$ molecules/(cm² s).⁶⁹ The cleanliness of the n -butane gas is controlled by QMS. The largest signal in the n -butane mass spectrum at $m/z = 43$ was used in all time-dependent QMS measurements of n -butane.

The ILs studied here were purchased from IoLiTec Ionic Liquids Technologies GmbH ($[C_3C_1Im][Tf_2N]$, $[C_2C_1Im][PF_6]$,

[C₄C₁Im][PF₆], and [C₈C₁Im][PF₆]; purity >99.5%), or synthesized according to previously published procedures ([C₂C₁Im][Tf₂N] and [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N]).⁷² The purity and surface cleanliness of all ILs was further confirmed by XPS. A macroscopic film (≈ 1.0 mm thickness) of each IL was prepared on the polycrystalline Ni sample plate by spreading the IL with a Pasteur pipette. To ensure homogeneous spreading of the room temperature solid [C₂C₁Im][PF₆], the sample plate was gently heated.

III. BEAM CHARACTERIZATION AND FLUX MEASUREMENT

The beam flux can be measured with the beam monitor mounted in the analysis chamber (as described in Sec. II). This device works similar to a pitot tube (stagnation tube), which is, e.g., used for velocity measurements in aviation. When the molecular beam hits the orifice of the beam monitor (diameter: 1.00 mm), the pressure in the beam monitor rises and slowly reaches equilibrium (pressure values are typically taken after 20 min waiting time to ensure equilibrium), which means no net flux through the orifice, that is, the incoming gas flux R_{in} equals the outgoing flux R_{out} ,

$$R_{in} = R_{out}. \quad (1)$$

R_{in} is the sum of two components, one originating from the background pressure, R_{bp} , of the analysis chamber and one from the directed incoming molecular beam, R_{MB} ,

$$R_{MB} + R_{bp} = R_{out}. \quad (2)$$

Under the reasonable simplification that the background gas in the analysis chamber and the gas accumulated in the beam monitor consists solely of the same molecules (with mass m) as used in the molecular beam and that the temperature in both chambers is the same and constant, we obtain

$$R_{MB} = R_{out} - R_{bp} = \frac{p_{MB} - p_{bgr}}{\sqrt{2\pi mk_B T}} = \frac{\Delta p}{\sqrt{2\pi mk_B T}}. \quad (3)$$

p_{bgr} is the pressure measured in the beam monitor with the molecular beam blocked by the closed sample flag in front of the beam monitor orifice and p_{MB} is the beam monitor pressure measured with the open sample flag, that is, the central part of the molecular beam passes the orifice.

The beam monitor allows for determining the beam flux impinging on the sample surface as a function of the gas flux through the nozzle, as set by the gas flow controller (see Fig. S4 of the [supplementary material](#)). Moreover, we used the beam monitor to create a lateral profile map of the beam intensity on the sample (see Fig. 2). As a typical example with the *n*-butane beam (gas flow 1.0 SCCM and the beam aperture between stage 2 and 3 of 1.1 mm in diameter), the Δp values were recorded along a grid of positions adjusted at the beam monitor manipulator. These settings were also used for the King and Wells measurements in Sec. IV. To decrease the measurement time, the valve to the additional pumping in the beam monitor was left open, and thus, equilibrium was reached

FIG. 2. Contour plot of the intensity of the *n*-butane molecular beam (gas flow 1.0 SCCM, smallest beam defining orifice with a diameter of 1.1 mm) measured with the beam monitor. The beam monitor was moved along a grid of points with 0.5 mm spacing, and the system has been given a time of 1.5 min to equilibrate at each grid position. Due to additional differential pumping, the obtained Δp values cannot be converted into the *n*-butane flux (see the text). The inset at the top shows the beam profile in the *x*-direction at $z = 16.0$ mm and the inset on the right shows the one in the *z*-direction at $x = 7.5$ mm; the locations of the beam profiles are indicated in the contour plot by white dashed lines. The black solid lines in the insets show the convolution of a rectangular beam profile (dashed lines) and the theoretically expected broadening function of the beam monitor orifice.

faster (1.5 min equilibration time instead of 20 min with a closed valve). The Δp values from this experiment can therefore not directly be converted into the flux but allow for determining the profile. As one would expect, the shape of the beam in Fig. 2 appears to be round and symmetrical, and there is only very little intensity variation in the center of the beam. In the graph, the beam is broadened because of the finite diameter of the beam monitor orifice (1.00 mm). The black solid lines in the insets of Fig. 2 show the convolution of a 3.4 mm wide rectangular beam profile (indicated by dashed lines) and the broadening function of the beam monitor orifice. The excellent agreement indicates that we have a sharp rectangular beam profile, as indicated by the dashed lines. The determined beam diameter of 3.4 mm is in perfect agreement with the expectations from the geometrical parameters of the molecular beam, considering the distances of the beam monitor and the chosen beam aperture (diameter of 1.1 mm) to the skimmer, that is, 487 mm and 159 mm, respectively. This corresponds to an opening angle of the circular beam of 0.2°.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following, we will apply our new beam setup to study the temperature-dependent trapping of *n*-butane on frozen ILs, namely, [C₈C₁Im][PF₆], [C₄C₁Im][PF₆], and [C₂C₁Im][PF₆], in the temperature range from 85 K to 125 K. As discussed previously, the surface structures of the ILs in their solid state are expected to be very similar

to the ones in the liquid state.⁶⁹ First, we will address the time-dependent trapping probability $S(t)$, followed by the temperature-dependence of the trapping probability S_0 in the zero-coverage limit. From the obtained values, we will determine the desorption energies using a new analysis approach. The obtained results will then be compared to the earlier results on similar ILs with $[\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]^-$ instead of $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ as an anion.

A. Time-dependent trapping probability

The trapping probability S is defined as the probability for an incoming molecule to get trapped in a physisorbed state, which is given by the ratio of the adsorption rate R_{ads} to the impingement rate R_{MB} ,

$$S = \frac{R_{ads}}{R_{MB}}. \quad (4)$$

In the case of chemisorption, this ratio is called the sticking probability (or the sticking coefficient). The symbol S is common for both quantities, and occasionally, they are also used as synonyms in the literature. In this work, the trapping probability was determined by the direct method of King and Wells,⁷¹ which is based on the time-dependent measurement of the partial pressure of gas molecules, typically with a QMS.

The trapping probability measurement follows a sequence of opening and closing of two flags (simple rotatable shutters) (see Fig. 3 for the adsorption of *n*-butane on $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$). The “beam flag” is placed behind the skimmer so that the beam can already be stopped before it reaches the analysis chamber, and the “sample flag” is located right in front of the sample so that it can block the beam before reaching the sample surface.

In the beginning of the experiment ($t \approx -40$ s), both flags are closed, and the beam cannot enter the analysis chamber. The QMS only measures a background signal, which can later be set as $p = 0$. At $t \approx -20$ s, the beam flag is opened; so, now, the molecular beam can enter the analysis chamber. The sample flag remains closed, and all incoming molecules are scattered on its inert surface, which leads to a pressure increase Δp_{MB} in the analysis chamber. At $t = 0$ s, the sample flag is also opened so that the gas molecules directly impinge on the sample surface. Adsorption on the sample surface leads to a sudden pressure drop Δp_0 because molecules adsorbing on the surface do not contribute to the signal measured by the QMS; if all impinging molecules would adsorb (that is, $S = 1$), the pressure would drop to zero. The ratio of Δp_0 and Δp_{MB} directly gives the trapping probability in the zero-coverage limit S_0 ,

$$S_0 = \frac{\Delta p_0}{\Delta p_{MB}}. \quad (5)$$

S can depend on coverage (and therefore also on time in a King and Wells experiment). Equivalently to (5), it can be written as

$$S(t) = \frac{\Delta p(t)}{\Delta p_{MB}}. \quad (6)$$

In our trapping probability measurements on ILs, we distinguish three characteristic behaviors A, B, and C: In case A [Fig. 3(a)],

FIG. 3. Exemplary King and Wells measurements with *n*-butane on $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ at (a) 85 K, (b) 102 K, and (c) 125 K representing cases A, B, and C (see the text). The most intense fragment ($m/z = 43$) of *n*-butane was used to monitor the partial pressure. A linear background was subtracted from all curves. The opening and closing of the two flags are marked in blue, and the characteristic pressure differences are marked in green (for details, see the main text). A schematic of the beam is shown at the top of the figure; the distances from the skimmer and the aperture to the sample are 487 mm and 159 mm, respectively.

the trapping probability is coverage-independent (that is, identical adsorption occurs in the mono- and multilayer regime), which means that the pressure stays constant as long as the sample flag is open. Closing the sample flag ($t \approx 60$ s) brings the pressure back to its original level before opening the sample flag ($p = \Delta p_{MB}$) because then the molecular beam is again scattered on the inert sample flag.

In case B [Fig. 3(b)], the pressure drops initially (Δp_0) but rises afterward until it reaches the level it had before opening the sample flag ($p = \Delta p_{MB}$). For our systems, we attribute this effect to partial desorption from the sample surface, yielding a steady state between adsorbing and desorbing molecules. This becomes apparent by looking at the pressure response on closing the sample flag ($t \approx 60$ s): The pressure rises above the level it had before opening the sample flag ($p > \Delta p_{MB}$) because in addition to the molecules being scattered from the sample flag, the QMS also detects molecules desorbing from the sample surface while the adsorption rate has dropped to zero. In

case B, the trapping probability determined by the King and Wells method is not the trapping probability in its narrow sense. We therefore denote it as net trapping probability, S^{net} , which will later be used to determine adsorption energies. In the time interval $t = 20$ s–60 s in Fig. 3(b), with $S^{net}(t) = 0$ and $p = \Delta p_{MB}$, the system is in a steady state: The rate of adsorption from the molecular beam to the sample surface is equal to the rate of desorption from the sample surface into the analysis chamber.

In case C [Fig. 3(c)], the trapping probability is zero [$S_0 = S(t) = 0$]. Consequently, no initial pressure drop Δp_0 is observable when the sample flag is opened ($t = 0$ s), and the pressure does also not increase in the moment of closing the sample flag ($t \approx 60$ s). However on close inspection of the measurement curve, a very small pressure change in $0.04 \cdot \Delta p_{MB}$ is always visible at $t = 0$ s and $t \approx 60$ s, which is independent of sample nature and temperature and only occurs with liquid nitrogen cooling of the manipulator. We thus attribute this small pressure change not to adsorption at the sample surface but to an experimental artifact. We always corrected for this effect in the following trapping probability analysis. After closing the beam flag at $t \approx 80$ s, the pressure returns to the initial background pressure.

In the measurement series for frozen $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$ (Fig. 4, left) and $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$ (Fig. 4, right), a gradual transition from case A to case C occurs with increasing temperature. At low temperature (89 K–91 K), the trapping probability $S = 0.86 \pm 0.02$ is independent of coverage. In the measurement at 95 K, the pressure increases after the initial pressure drop until the first layer is filled (indicated by an arrow). As soon as the first layer is filled, the desorption rate (and the

pressure) stays constant. This observation is somehow equivalent to a zeroth order multilayer desorption in temperature-programmed desorption (TPD). Since the net trapping probability is still larger than zero, the multilayer continues to grow until the end of the experiment, albeit with a smaller trapping probability. Above 99 K, the transition to case B is completed for both ILs, which means, the steady state with $S^{net} = 0$ is reached before the first layer is filled completely. At higher temperatures, the increasing desorption rate already influences the initial trapping probability S_0^{net} (as will be discussed later), which decreases with increasing temperature. At 120 K for $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$ and 115 K for $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$, the transition to case C is complete and no trapping is observed any more. While the behavior is similar for both ILs, the transition from one case to the other occurs at lower temperatures for $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$ than for $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$.

B. Temperature-dependence of S_0

The difference between the two ILs, $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$ and $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$, becomes more apparent if the initial trapping probability is plotted vs the sample temperature (Fig. 5). We also included data for $[C_2C_1Im][PF_6]$ and for comparison, also our previously published data for three different $[C_nC_1Im][Tf_2N]$ ILs with $n = 2, 3$, and 8.⁶⁹ The latter have $[Tf_2N]^-$ as an anion instead of $[PF_6]^-$. The overall behavior of the ILs with $n = 3$ –8 is similar: At temperatures well below 100 K, a plateau with constant $S_0 = 0.88 \pm 0.05$ is observed for all ILs with $n \geq 3$. Above a certain temperature, which depends on the particular IL, S_0 starts to decrease until it reaches

FIG. 4. Temperature dependent trapping probability measurements of *n*-butane on $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$ (left) and $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$ (right). The most intense fragment ($m/z = 43$) of *n*-butane was used to monitor the partial pressure. A linear background was subtracted from all curves.

FIG. 5. Temperature-dependent initial trapping probability S_0^{net} of n -butane on various ILs after background subtraction (see the text). The dashed lines are fits to the data [according to Eq. (16) in Sec. IV C]. This fitting model was used to calculate the desorption energies for the ILs (Table I). The data for the $[\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ -ILs were adapted from Ref. 69.

zero. As in our previous publication,⁶⁹ we describe this behavior using the characteristic temperature $T_{50\%}$ at which S_0 of a specific IL has dropped to 50% of its initial value (Table I). The two ILs with an octyl side chain — $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ — have very similar $T_{50\%}$ values, 110 K and 111 K, respectively (the difference falls within the margin of error of ± 1 K). This shows that in this case, the adsorption/desorption dynamics are dominated by the van der Waals interactions of n -butane with the alkyl chains in the cation, while the nature of the anions does not appear to play a decisive role. For $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$, $T_{50\%}$ is 107 K, which lies in between the values for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_3\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$. The decrease in the characteristic temperature is attributed to weaker van der Waals interactions of n -butane with the shorter alkyl chains.

The two investigated ILs with $n = 2$ — $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ — show a completely different behavior, that is, no trapping is observed even in the temperature range of multilayer

TABLE I. Characteristic $T_{50\%}$ values and desorption energies E_{des} determined by the method described in Sec. IV C using the prefactor $\nu = 1.4 \cdot 10^{14}$ 1/s from Ref. 69 for the fitting process.

IL	$T_{50\%}$ (K)	E_{des} (kJ/mol)
$[\text{C}_3\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$	104	26.8
$[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$	107	27.7
$[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$	110	28.6
$[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$	111	28.8

condensation (case A) on the other ILs. The two ILs have in common that the longest alkyl substituent is only an ethyl chain. In line with our previous study, we suggest that for both ILs, the interaction of n -butane with all IL constituents (ethyl chain, cationic head group, and anion) is weak, resulting in an insufficient residence time for the formation of condensation nuclei. Since $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ shows the same behavior as $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$, we conclude that the polar character of the surface is responsible for the weak interaction.

C. Determination of the desorption energy

As mentioned earlier, the King and Wells method is widely used to determine sticking or trapping probabilities, that is, the probability for an incoming molecule to adsorb on the surface. Precisely, this is only true if desorption is negligible because desorbing molecules will contribute to the partial pressure of the molecule in the vacuum chamber. Hence, the quantity measured with the King and Wells method is also denoted as the net trapping probability, S^{net} , defined as

$$S^{\text{net}} = \frac{R_{\text{ads}} - R_{\text{des}}}{R_{\text{MB}}}, \quad (7)$$

where R_{ads} is the adsorption rate, R_{des} is the desorption rate, and R_{MB} is the impingement rate of the molecular beam (note that S^{net} was denoted as S^* in our previous publication⁶⁹). At low temperatures (LT, $T \approx 90$ K), desorption is negligible in our experiments. Otherwise, an increase in the partial pressure would be observable after closing the sample flag, as it is the case for higher temperatures [compare also Figs. 3(a) and 3(b)]. The net trapping probability at LT, S^{LT} , is therefore equal to the trapping probability in its narrow sense,

$$S^{\text{LT}} = \frac{R_{\text{ads}}}{R_{\text{MB}}} \Leftrightarrow R_{\text{ads}} = S^{\text{LT}} \cdot R_{\text{MB}}. \quad (8)$$

Assuming that the adsorption rate is independent of temperature in the region of interest, we obtain

$$S^{\text{net}} = \frac{S^{\text{LT}} \cdot R_{\text{MB}} - R_{\text{des}}}{R_{\text{MB}}} = S^{\text{LT}} - \frac{R_{\text{des}}}{R_{\text{MB}}}. \quad (9)$$

If desorption follows first order kinetics, the desorption rate is given by

$$R_{\text{des}} = \theta \cdot \nu \cdot e^{-\frac{E_{\text{des}}}{RT}}, \quad (10)$$

where θ is the adsorbate coverage, ν is a preexponential frequency factor, R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature, and E_{des} is the activation energy for desorption. For non-activated adsorption, as it is typically the case for physisorption, the latter is equal to the binding energy of the adsorbate.

In a more general approach, the change in coverage $d\theta$ during a time interval dt is given by the difference of the adsorption and desorption rates,

$$d\theta = R_{\text{ads}}dt - R_{\text{des}}dt = (S^{\text{net}} \cdot R_{\text{MB}})dt. \quad (11)$$

Integration yields

$$\theta(t) = R_{MB} \cdot \int_0^t S^{net} dt. \quad (12)$$

$t = 0$ is defined as the time when the sample flag is opened. In our previous publication,⁶⁹ we obtained values for $\theta(t)$ by numerical integration of the $S^{net}(t)$ curve until time t . If the desorption energy E_{des} does not depend on coverage, the desorption rate R_{des} increases linearly with coverage, and thus, S^{net} decreases linearly in an S^{net} vs θ plot. In this case, the (constant) slopes of the $S^{net}(\theta)$ decrease for different temperatures can be analyzed in an Arrhenius analysis. In our previous study, this approach worked quite well for *n*-butane adsorption on $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ in the temperature range between 106 K and 93 K, yielding a desorption energy of 29 ± 3 kJ/mol and a prefactor of $1.4 \cdot 10^{14 \pm 2}$ 1/s.⁶⁹ It should, however, be noted that this analysis only can be applied if (a) the trapping probability is coverage-independent over a large coverage range and (b) the desorption rate is large enough to be measurable but low enough to allow for the formation of a considerable adsorbate layer; this was the main reason why our previous analysis only worked for $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ but not for the ILs with shorter chains.⁶⁹

In this work, we now want to focus on the low coverage limit to directly access the initial net trapping probability S_0^{net} in the time interval $[0; t_m]$ required to measure the first data point after opening the sample flag (t_m is the measurement time per data point, that is, 0.5 s). During this time interval, a small coverage θ_0 already builds up on the surface (even at the lowest temperature, θ_0 is only 3% of a closed *n*-butane layer), yielding a certain desorption rate $R_{des,0}$ and $R_{des,0}$ will increase with progressing time. In a first approximation, both are best represented by their values in the center of the time interval, i.e., at $t_m/2$,

$$\begin{aligned} R_{des,0} &= R_{des} \left(t = \frac{t_m}{2} \right) = \theta \left(t = \frac{t_m}{2} \right) \cdot \nu \cdot e^{-\frac{E_{des}}{RT}} \\ &= R_{MB} \cdot \left(\int_0^{\frac{t_m}{2}} S_0^{net} dt \right) \cdot \nu \cdot e^{-\frac{E_{des}}{RT}}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Under the approximation that S_0^{net} remains constant in this short time interval, it can be written as follows:

$$R_{des,0} = R_{MB} \cdot S_0^{net} \cdot \frac{t_m}{2} \cdot \nu \cdot e^{-\frac{E_{des}}{RT}}. \quad (14)$$

For S_0^{net} , we then obtain

$$S_0^{net} = \frac{R_{des,0}}{R_{MB}} = S^{LT} - S_0^{net} \cdot \frac{t_m}{2} \cdot \nu \cdot e^{-\frac{E_{des}}{RT}} \quad (15)$$

$$\Rightarrow S_0^{net} = \frac{S^{LT}}{1 + \frac{t_m}{2} \cdot \nu \cdot e^{-\frac{E_{des}}{RT}}}. \quad (16)$$

This expression provides a model description of the measurement data in Fig. 5. A value for S^{LT} can be extracted from the

measurements at LT, and t_m is known from the experimental conditions to be 0.50 s. Therefore, only two unknowns remain, E_{des} and ν , which are (unfortunately) strongly coupled in this equation. Thus, it is necessary to make an assumption for one of them to obtain unambiguous fitting results. In our previous publication, we derived $\nu = 1.4 \cdot 10^{14 \pm 2}$ 1/s for $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ from an Arrhenius analysis, based on the assumption of a coverage-independent trapping probability.⁶⁹ For the analysis in this work, we assume that this prefactor is applicable for all of the ILs.

The fit curves according to Eq. (16) are shown in Fig. 5, and the resulting desorption energies are summarized in Table I. Although the absolute uncertainty in activation energies is estimated to be ± 2 kJ/mol (due to the uncertainty of the prefactor and the absolute temperature scale), the uncertainty in differences of derived activation energy values is only about ± 0.3 kJ/mol. Previously, we used an Arrhenius analysis to determine the desorption energy of $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ to be 29 ± 3 kJ/mol;⁶⁹ with our newly developed method for the zero-coverage limit, we obtain 28.6 ± 2 kJ/mol assuming the same prefactor. Considering the margin of error of the evaluations, the agreement of this result is very satisfactory.

Table I shows that E_{des} increases from 26.8 kJ/mol for $[C_3C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ over 27.7 kJ/mol for $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$ to 28.6 kJ/mol for $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ and 28.8 kJ/mol for $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$. The length of the alkyl substituent clearly correlates with the desorption energy: the longer the alkyl chain, the higher the desorption energy, and thus, the stronger the binding of *n*-butane on the IL surface. We assume that the corresponding interaction potentials also hold for the liquid state due to the similarity between frozen and liquid surfaces.⁶⁹ Our results clearly show that the interaction is dominated by van der Waals forces between *n*-butane and the chemically similar alkyl chains of the IL cations. The difference found for the two $[C_8C_1Im]$ -ILs lies in the order of the margin of error. This finding corroborates our interpretation that the interaction of *n*-butane with the anion is irrelevant for the bonding mechanism. The very small difference between $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ and $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$ could be rationalized by the slightly larger surface enrichment of the octyl chain in ILs with smaller anions such as $[PF_6]^-$ compared to ILs with larger anions such as $[Tf_2N]^-$.^{33,73} Since the difference is smaller than the margin of error, this interpretation, however, has to be treated with great caution.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We present a novel multi-analysis UHV apparatus dedicated for the investigation of gas molecules interacting with vacuum-compatible liquid surfaces. The system comprises a vertically mounted supersonic molecular beam for the investigation of horizontally mounted liquid samples at normal beam incidence. The flux of the molecular beam can be determined with a beam monitor, which can also be used to measure the beam profile; in the here presented experiments using *n*-butane, a very sharp circular profile with a diameter of 3.4 mm in the sample plane is achieved. A rotatable mass spectrometer is installed, allowing for a variety of molecular beam scattering and adsorption studies. Additionally, an integrated XPS setup is used for chemical analysis and enables future combined experiments.

Using this new apparatus, we determined the trapping probabilities of *n*-butane on $[C_nC_1Im][PF_6]$ ILs ($n = 2, 4,$ and 8) in the temperature range of 85 K–125 K by the so-called King and Wells method. On $[C_2C_1Im][PF_6]$, no trapping of *n*-butane is observed. The same behavior was previously also found for $[C_2C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ and explained by a too short *n*-butane residence time for the formation of condensation nuclei.⁶⁹ On $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$ and $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$, the adsorption characteristics are temperature-dependent: *n*-butane grows in multilayers at low temperatures (≈ 90 K), while at temperatures above 120 K, the desorption rate becomes too high to observe trapping on the IL surfaces.

For $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$, the initial net trapping probability starts to decrease at lower temperatures than for $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$. This finding shows that van der Waals interactions with the alkyl side chain of the cation dominate the adsorption process. The decrease in trapping probability with decreasing side chain length can be described by the characteristic temperature values $T_{50\%}$ at which the initial net trapping probability has dropped to 50% of its maximum value. We obtain values of $T_{50\%} = 107$ K for $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$ and 110 K for $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$. The value for $[C_8C_1Im][PF_6]$ is almost identical to the value of 111 K found for $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ in a previous study.⁶⁹ We thus conclude that the nature of the anion does not seem to play a significant role for the adsorption process, which is not surprising due to the pronounced surface enrichment of the octyl chains for both ILs.

Based on the assumption that the initial trapping probability in its narrow sense is temperature-independent in the investigated temperature range, we attribute the decrease in the observed net trapping probability with increasing temperature solely to the increasing desorption rate. From this temperature-dependence, we determine the desorption energy of *n*-butane in the low-coverage limit on the different ILs using a simple analysis procedure. The resulting desorption energies on the different ILs show the same trend as found for the $T_{50\%}$ values, that is, they increase with increasing alkyl chain length. For $[C_8C_1Im][Tf_2N]$, we previously determined the desorption energy in an Arrhenius analysis under the assumption that the trapping probability in its narrow sense is coverage-independent.⁶⁹ The results of the previous Arrhenius analysis and the new approach focusing on the low-coverage limit are in very good agreement.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

See the [supplementary material](#) for the schematic drawing of the vacuum system (Fig. S1) with the specification of the components (Table S1); photo plus drawings of the manipulator and sample holder (Fig. S2); contour plots of the molecular beam profile (Fig. S3); and the *n*-butane beam flux measured with the beam monitor as a function of the gas flow in the mass flow controller (Fig. S4).

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

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